

Models and phenomenology of neutrino polarizability

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arXiv: [2210.05706](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.05706), [2508.16724](https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.16724)

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Electromagnetic neutrino interactions

[Non-standard interactions as EFT: 1812.02778]

$$\frac{C_{ij}^{(5)}}{\Lambda} (\bar{\nu}_i \sigma^{\mu\nu} P_L \nu_j) F_{\mu\nu}$$

$$\frac{C_{ij}^{(7)}}{\Lambda^3} (\bar{\nu}_i P_L \nu_j) F_{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}$$

- Point unequivocally to a new scale
- Lead to interesting signatures

Electromagnetic neutrino interactions

The same New Physics will generate contributions to the neutrino mass
(can be disentangled for dipoles)

- Point unequivocally to a new scale
- Lead to interesting signatures

Electromagnetic neutrino interactions

Toy model: light pseudoscalar (ALP)

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi \supset \frac{1}{2} c_\nu^{ij} (\bar{\nu}_i P_L \nu_j) \phi - \frac{\alpha}{8\pi} \frac{c_\gamma}{f_\phi} \phi F_{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} + \text{h.c.}$$

Matching to EFT

$$c_\nu^{ij} \propto \frac{m_\nu^{ij}}{f_\phi} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{c_{ij}^{(7)}}{\Lambda^3} \simeq m_\nu^{ij} c_\gamma \frac{1}{m_\phi^2 f_\phi^2}$$

Electromagnetic neutrino interactions

Toy model: light pseudoscalar (ALP)

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Enhanced polarizability if scale is small
and mediator is light

$$f_\phi \sim m_\nu$$

(ideally)

Minimal model

[2210.05706]

Global lepton number

Minimal model

[2210.05706]

Inverse seesaw

Small mass from
small breaking
and/or
small mixing

Neutrino mass

$$m_\nu \simeq f_\phi s_\alpha^2$$

Lepton number is broken by S:

$$S = (f_\phi + i\phi)/\sqrt{2}$$

Heavy EW triplets
carrying lepton
number

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi \supset -\frac{9\alpha}{64\pi} n_\Psi s_w^2 \frac{\phi}{f_\phi} \tilde{F}_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu}$$

Bound from colliders

$$f_\phi \gtrsim 100 \text{ GeV}$$

Minimal model

[2210.05706]

$$\frac{C_{ij}^{(7)}}{\Lambda^3} \simeq i \left(\frac{1}{7.3 \text{ GeV}} \right)^3 \left(\frac{100 \text{ GeV}}{f_\phi} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{1 \text{ keV}}{m_\phi} \right)^2 \times n_\Psi \times \frac{(m_\nu)_{ij}}{0.1 \text{ eV}}$$

Less Minimal model

[2210.05706]

$U(1) \times U'(1)$

$$\frac{C_{ij}^{(7)}}{\Lambda^3} \simeq \left(\frac{1}{16 \text{ MeV}} \right)^3 \left(\frac{100 \text{ GeV}}{f'_\phi} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ keV}}{f_\phi} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ keV}}{m_{\phi_1}} \right)^2 \times n_\Psi c_\theta s_\theta \times \left(\frac{(m_\nu)_{ij}}{0.1 \text{ eV}} \right)$$

At this point...

We have a model for enhanced neutrino polarizability that can compensate for small neutrino mass suppressions

Independently of the model, it leads to novel signatures

Phenomenology is defined by three parameters: m_ϕ , c_ν , $g_{\phi\gamma} = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \frac{c_\gamma}{f_\phi}$

Focus on MeV and larger masses, where 'terrestrial' exp are relevant

Lighter masses affect cosmological and astrophysical observables

Neutrino specific
(horizontal lines)

ALP specific
(vertical lines)

Neutrino scattering
(Diagonal lines)

Meson decays

Beam dumps, photon searches

MiniBooNE, DM detectors,...

Search at DUNE-ND

[2508.16724]

Large flux of neutrinos

Scattering on target

Emission of extra photon

Search at DUNE-ND

[2508.16724]

Scattering on electrons
2 EM showers signature

Coherent scattering on Argon
1 EM shower signature

Build template in total EM energy and separation angle

Search at DUNE-ND

[2508.16724]

Polarizability leads to more energetic and separated showers than SM bkg

1 EM: S/\sqrt{B}

2 EM: S/\sqrt{B}

Search at DUNE-ND

[2508.16724]

Search at DUNE-ND

[2508.16724]

$m_\phi = 50 \text{ MeV}$

$m_\phi = 1 \text{ GeV}$

Moving forward

- Photon - electron separation? Would improve bkg rejection
- Better control of bkg systematics
- Optimized binning - or unbinned maximum likelihood estimator

Work in Progress

- ISS naturally includes light - heavy neutrino transitions \rightarrow displaced vertices from HNL decays inside NR

See also M. Borrello's talk later today!

Backups

Minimal model: Inverse seesaw

ISS: L and R Weyl fermion, carry global lepton number

$$-\mathcal{L}_Y \supset y_\nu \bar{L} \tilde{H}^\dagger N_R + \bar{N}_L M_N N_R + \lambda_R \bar{N}_R^c S N_R + \lambda_L \bar{N}_L S N_L^c + \text{h.c.}$$

Lepton number is broken by S: $S = (f_\phi + i\phi)/\sqrt{2}$

Mass matrix

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & M_D & 0 \\ M_D^\top & \mu_R & M_N^\top \\ 0 & M_N & \mu_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Dirac mass

$$M_D = y_\nu v / \sqrt{2}$$

Breaking term

$$\mu_{L,R} = \lambda_{L,R} f_\phi / \sqrt{2}$$

Eigenvalues hierarchy

$$\mu_{L,R} \ll M_D \ll M_N$$

Minimal model: Inverse seesaw

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Lepton number is broken by S: $S = (f_\phi + i\phi)/\sqrt{2}$

Lightest neutrino

$$\nu \simeq c_\alpha \nu_L - s_\alpha N_R \quad \text{Eigenstate}$$

$$m_\nu \simeq f_\phi s_\alpha^2 \quad \text{Mass}$$

$$\tan \alpha \simeq \frac{M_D}{M_N} \quad \text{Mixing}$$

ALP coupling

$$\mu_L \rightarrow i\mu_L \phi / f_\phi$$

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi \supset -\frac{i}{2} (m_\nu)_{ij} (\bar{\nu}_i P_L \nu_j) \frac{\phi}{f_\phi} + \text{h.c.}$$

Minimal model: EW triplets

Heavy EW triplets carrying lepton number

$$\mathcal{L}_{\Psi_R} = -\frac{1}{2} y_{\Psi} S \overline{(\Psi_R^a)^c} \Psi_R^a + \text{h.c.}$$

Mass of triplets generated from the scalar

$$M_{\Psi} = y_{\Psi} \langle S \rangle = y_{\Psi} f_{\phi} / \sqrt{2}$$

Coupling to SU(2) bosons through triangle anomaly

$$\mathcal{L}_{\phi} \supset -\frac{9\alpha}{64\pi} n_{\Psi} \frac{\phi}{f_{\phi}} \tilde{W}_{\mu\nu}^a W^{a\mu\nu}$$

Minimal model: EW triplets

Heavy EW triplets carrying lepton number

$$\mathcal{L}_{\Psi_R} = -\frac{1}{2} y_{\Psi} S \overline{(\Psi_R^a)^c} \Psi_R^a + \text{h.c.}$$

...rotating to photons

$$\mathcal{L}_{\phi} \supset -\frac{9\alpha}{64\pi} n_{\Psi} s_w^2 \frac{\phi}{f_{\phi}} \tilde{F}_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu}$$

Problem: EW can be produced at colliders, stringent limit on scale

$$f_{\phi} \gtrsim 100 \text{ GeV}$$